

Tool for Data and Knowledge Exploration Assessment

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1. Introduction

“The Equal-Life Toolbox web page aims to provide resources and tools to help understand the impact of environmental and social factors (the “exposome”) on children’s development and mental health. The site offers researchers and stakeholders a guidebook, tools, and explorables to explore the findings and concepts developed in the Equal-Life project. It serves as a platform to integrate and analyse data, supporting the creation of more supportive environments for children.”

Proposal Equal-Life 2020

The main objective of the Equal-Life Toolbox is to provide a digital platform that enables the exploration of exposome factors and their impact on children’s cognitive development and mental health. It aims to translate complex scientific findings into actionable insights for various stakeholders, including policymakers, researchers, and practitioners. The toolbox serves as a central resource consolidating knowledge, methodologies, and tools developed within the Equal-Life project to inform interventions aimed at improving children’s mental health and cognitive development. Ultimately, it fosters supportive environments that prioritise children’s mental health and cognitive development, contributing to a healthier future for all children.

The toolbox comprises a Web-based data and knowledge exploration application, as well as a guidance document suitable for broad use and adaptable for new data and methods, and for disseminations of results (*Deliverables:9.3 – D9.5*).

The main aim of this document is to describe all the actions put in place to evaluate the toolbox’s current state of the art and the impact of stakeholder feedback on its development, particularly in enhancing its usability and applicability to meet the diverse needs of users involved in interventions considering children’s mental health and cognitive development.

The toolbox comprises a web-based data and knowledge exploration application, complemented by a guidance document designed for broad use and for the dissemination of project results (*Deliverables D9.3–D9.5*). Its overall structure has been conceived to support different types of users in accessing, understanding, and navigating the wide range of outputs produced within the Equal-Life project.

In defining the structure and organisation of the Toolbox, particular attention has been given to a number of key design considerations, including accessibility, clarity of structure, functional coherence, and integration of contents. These aspects were taken into account to ensure that users with diverse professional backgrounds—such as researchers, policymakers, practitioners, and other stakeholders—can meaningfully engage with the platform and its resources. The Toolbox has been designed to provide structured access to the project’s outputs, including

concept documents, definitions, logic frameworks, scientific publications, analytical approaches, data production and harmonisation protocols, aggregate statistics, and results of analytical models. Special care has been taken to organise these materials in a way that supports navigation across different levels of detail and facilitates connections between results and the tools or documents in which they are described.

Another guiding principle in the design of the Toolbox has been its integration with the Guidebook, with the aim of creating a coherent digital environment in which users can move smoothly between theoretical concepts, research findings, and practical tools. This integration supports interpretability and helps users contextualise analytical results within the broader conceptual framework of the exposome and children's mental health and cognitive development.

Throughout the development process, the structure and content of the Toolbox have been discussed and refined through repeated interactions with stakeholders during workshops, training sessions, and other project activities. While no formal or standalone assessment has been conducted, stakeholder feedback collected during these interactions has been used as a qualitative reference to inform design choices, clarify descriptions, and improve overall coherence. In this way, the Toolbox reflects an iterative and participatory approach, in which usability, relevance, and practical applicability were continuously considered alongside scientific robustness.

1.1 Integration of research findings and practical tools

A critical objective of the Equal-Life project was to effectively translate its research findings into practical tools that could be used by stakeholders to inform policies and interventions. This was primarily achieved through the development of the Equal-Life Toolbox and the accompanying Guidebook, which were designed to be seamlessly integrated.

Key aspects of this integration included:

- **Toolbox as a Gateway to Project Outputs:** The toolbox was conceived as a central platform providing access to the Equal-Life project's various outputs and results. This included concept documents, definitions, logic frameworks, scientific publications, analytical approaches, data production and harmonisation protocols, aggregate statistics, and results of analytical models. The goal was to make these complex research outputs accessible to a diverse audience, including those without a strong technical background.
- **Guidebook as a Contextual Resource:** The Guidebook was developed as an interactive, web-based resource that is seamlessly integrated with the Toolbox. It aimed to provide

the theoretical background, explanations, and context necessary for stakeholders to understand and effectively use the tools and interpret the research findings. The integration aimed to create a unified digital environment where users could easily navigate between theoretical concepts, research findings, and practical tools.

- **Mapping Research to Tools:** A key part of the integration process involved mapping the project's research results to the corresponding tools and content within the toolbox and guidebook. This ensured that users could easily find the relevant information and tools based on their specific needs and questions.
- **Knowledge Translation:** The project recognised the need to translate complex scientific content into a language accessible to stakeholders with varying backgrounds. This was addressed through clear explanations, summaries, real-world applications, intuitive data visualisations, case studies, interactive materials, and multilingual training.

The integration of research findings and practical tools was an ongoing process, informed by continuous feedback from stakeholders. The aim was to ensure that the toolbox served as a practical and evidence-based resource that would enable stakeholders to better understand and address the effects of physical, internal, and social exposures on children's mental health. The project also explored the potential for the toolbox to incorporate data from both Equal-Life and other existing sources, further enhancing its utility. Ultimately, the methodology prioritised creating tools that were not only grounded in rigorous research but also directly applicable to real-world policymaking and intervention design.

2. The final version of the structure and content of the toolbox

This section presents the content structure currently available in the toolbox, following the same structure as the toolbox website in its current form. The present arrangement is to be considered definitive in terms of structure and in the process of being finalized with regards to contents. The content has been carefully transferred from the scientific documentation produced during the project. This document aims solely to showcase the state of the art of the toolbox and the guidebook, without intending to represent the state of the art of the scientific content.

The documentation related to the toolbox's content are available from the official website of Equal-Life - <https://www.equal-life.eu/en>, at the CORDIS European portal - <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/874724> and in the Zenodo repository ([https://zenodo.org/communities/equal life/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest](https://zenodo.org/communities/equal%20life/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest)).

2.1 Homepage

Figure 1 The main section as starting point in the home website of the toolbox

The homepage serves as the gateway to the toolbox (Figure 1), providing access to the main sections. It aims to introduce the tool, its purpose, and functionalities.

The homepage (<https://www.equal-life-toolbox.eu/>) of the Equal-Life Toolbox website provides access to the three main sections (Figure 2) through a path menu:

- **Guidebook:** Offers detailed concepts and definitions related to the exposome and its impact on children's mental health and cognitive development. It is a comprehensive resource to help users understand how environmental and social factors contribute to health outcomes. The Guidebook is designed to be an interactive, web-based resource seamlessly integrated with the Toolbox.
- **Findings:** This section is designed to present the research findings from the Equal-Life project in an interactive and accessible way, often using visual elements like charts and diagrams to help users understand complex data.
- **Tools:** This area provides access to the various software, libraries, and pipelines produced within the project to support data analysis and collection. It acts as a gallery showing the different tools of Equal-Life, with descriptions and links to dedicated pages or original hosting platforms. Tutorials and contact information for clarifications are also intended to be available.

Figure 2 shows the access to the three main pages from the toolbox (home). As described in the main text, there are three main sections: "Guidebook", "Findings" and "Tools". The main sections are accessible by a button linked to the specific webpages.

2.2 Guidebook

The Equal-Life Toolbox website's Guidebook page (<https://www.equal-life-toolbox.eu/guidebook>) provides users with detailed concepts and definitions related to the exposome and its impact on children's mental health and cognitive development. It is a comprehensive resource to help users understand how environmental and social factors contribute to health outcomes. The guidebook is structured to facilitate the exploration of these ideas, offering insights into the key components of the exposome and the various influences on mental health.

The Guidebook page offers a structured menu that allows users to navigate through various sections related to the exposome, mental health, and cognitive development. The page includes an in-depth explanation of the main concepts and themes discussed in the guidebook. The detailed description complements the menu and enhances the user's understanding of complex topics. The menu provides easy access to different sections, making it user-friendly for those seeking specific information.

Q. Enter search term

Understanding the Exposome

What is the Exposome?
Materials and Methods
The Physical Domain
The Social Domain
The Internal Domain
Mental Health and Cognitive Development
The Role of Life Course
The Role of Mediators
Cumulative effects of various exposures
Glossary

Understanding Equal-Life main concepts and definitions

Explore in-depth concepts and definitions of the exposome as investigated in Equal-Life and its impacts on children's mental health and cognitive development. This information provides essential background to delve deeper to understand the findings and tools we have developed in Equal-Life. Navigate through the menu to access sections on the various exposures, mediators and outcomes related to mental health and cognitive development.

- [What is the exposome?](#) – Explore the concept of the exposome and the exposures it includes.
- [Materials and Methods](#) - Learn about how we studied the effects of exposures on the outcomes and the methods applied in the Equal-Life project.

Figure 3 shows the side menu for exploring the guidebook's main sections and the summary description of the different sections of the guidebook.

All sections of the guidebook are organised around topics (e.g., exposome, mental health, mediators, etc. – *more details are available in the D9.5*), and in-depth insights are linked to related resources in the toolbox.

For example, we use the “Exposome” topic (available at: <https://www.equal-life-toolbox.eu/exposome>) as an explanatory example:

The web page is structured to provide an in-depth overview of the Exposome concept. The page includes sections explaining the exposome, how it impacts health, particularly in children and adolescents, and its relevance to mental health and cognitive development. The content is organised with headings, supplemented by images and diagrams to help illustrate key points. The page also includes links to further resources and related sections within the toolbox, allowing for easy navigation and exploring related topics. These links guide users to additional sections of the toolbox, such as detailed explanations of related concepts or tools that can be used to investigate the exposome further by experts/researchers. The links are embedded in the relevant sections of the content, allowing for seamless navigation to further information that complements the main topics discussed on the page.

Figure 4 a screenshot of an example of the structure of one (in this case, “Exposome”) of the main sections of the guidebook in the online version. The main topic, “Exposome”, is introduced by a brief text.

2.3 The Findings

The Finding page on the Equal-Life Toolbox website has been developed and launched to disseminate the project's main outcomes effectively page (available at: <https://www.equal-life-toolbox.eu/finding> - See Figure 5). This page ensures that stakeholders, including researchers, policymakers, and educators, can easily access and utilize the project's results. By providing summaries, interactive exploration tools, and direct access to detailed reports and data, the page fulfills the project's objective of making its findings actionable and accessible to a broad audience.

The Findings section of the Equal-Life Toolbox has been revised to serve as the central access point for the interactive exploration of the project’s main results. It has been designed to translate complex scientific outputs into an accessible, visual, and action-oriented digital environment, enabling different categories of stakeholders to progressively explore, interpret, and apply the outcomes of the Equal-Life project.

2.3.1 Purpose and role of Findings page within the toolbox

The Findings page functions as a bridge between scientific evidence and practical use. It integrates results produced across multiple Work Packages and presents them in a structured way that supports exploration, interpretation, and policy-relevant reflection. The page complements the Guidebook by focusing on what has been found and what actions or reflections these findings may inform, rather than on theoretical definitions alone.

A dedicated “Findings and Call to Action” section has been introduced to explicitly connect research results with potential implications for practice and policy. This section has also served as the conceptual basis for the summary tables included in Deliverable D9.5, ensuring consistency between the online Toolbox and the formal project documentation.

2.3.2 Interactive and exploratory design

The Findings page has been redesigned as an interactive platform rather than a static repository of results. Visual elements, structured summaries, and navigable content blocks allow users to actively explore the outcomes instead of passively reading them. This approach supports different exploration paths depending on users’ interests, expertise, and objectives, while maintaining scientific coherence.

Recent updates have aligned the layout of the Findings section with the overall revision of the Toolbox interface, ensuring visual and functional consistency with the Tools and Guidebook pages.

2.3.3 Three-level documentation structure (L1–L3)

The Findings section implements a three-level documentation structure (L1–L3) that organises content according to increasing levels of detail and technical depth. This structure is consistently applied across the Toolbox and is aligned with the documentation strategy adopted in Deliverables D7.3, D9.5, and D9.7.

Level 1 (L1) – Findings Landing Page

The L1 level corresponds to the main Findings landing page. Its role is to provide a high-level overview of the project’s key outcomes and to act as an interactive entry point. Core messages and calls to action are presented in a visual and accessible format, guiding users towards deeper exploration while remaining understandable to non-technical audiences (see Figure 5).

Figure 5 The first section of the finding landing page.

Level 2 (L2) – Findings Insights and Syntheses

The L2 level is accessible from the landing page and offers more detailed explanations of the research results. It contains structured syntheses and interpretative texts that elaborate on key findings and their implications. These contents correspond to the “text to be included” across project deliverables and are designed to remain accessible while providing sufficient depth for informed use by policymakers, practitioners, and researchers (see Figure 6).

The bigger picture matters

Sleep, stress, self-regulation skills and restorative activities play a crucial **“mediating”** role between a child’s environment and their mental health.

As the middle step in the causal pathway between the environment and health, these factors act like a “volume switch” that can change, or modify, children’s mental health and cognitive development, for better or for worse.

Findings and call to action

Places matter

A child experiences “places” through the physical and social aspects of their home, school, digital world, leisure facilities, and neighbourhood, and the amount of time they spend there.

Psychological factors – such as children’s and families’ perceptions of place – for example, with regards to noise or safety, also affects mental health.

Findings and call to action

Age matters

Equal Life’s **Life course** approach highlights key exposures and vulnerabilities for each age group.

For example, we found that social factors affecting pregnant women can impact their children’s neurodevelopment and health outcomes. The family and home environment is particularly significant for under 3s, while after this age, the wider physical and social environment becomes increasingly important. The older the child, the farther they roam in the neighbourhood, and the more important access to greenspace becomes.

Findings and call to action

Equity matters

The concept of “exposome clusters” describes groups of children sharing physical and social exposures – such as living in an economically deprived neighbourhood, and having a mother with poor mental health. We found that children belonging to more economically deprived clusters had worse mental health, showing the importance of social equity in child health outcomes.

Findings and call to action

Figure 6 The interactive boxes of L2 contents present on the finding’s landing webpage.

Level 3 (L3) – Background Documentation and Full Outputs

The L3 level represents the most detailed layer of documentation. It includes background materials, full reports, scientific publications, and formal deliverables such as D7.3 and D9.5. Access to this level is primarily provided through direct links from the L1 and L2 pages, positioning the Findings section as a portal to the complete scientific evidence base of the project (see Figure 7-8).

Key Equal Life findings on “Places”

The urban/rural context

We found that exposure patterns vary between densely populated urban areas and less-populated rural areas. This means that certain exposures, such as green-space coverage, should be interpreted differently based on the urban or rural context. For example, the health impact of a small, well-designed park in an urban neighbourhood is different to a large expanse of agricultural land in a rural area.

Urban green space accessibility

Children’s access to urban greenspace is affected by neighbourhood layout, the size of the greenspace (smaller spaces are more accessible) and psychological factors such as attractiveness and motivation.

Figure 7 Example of the presentation of key Equal-Life findings related to Places. The left-hand side summarises the main insights at synthesis level (L1–L2), with a focus on the urban–rural context and children’s access to urban green spaces. The tiles on the right illustrate direct links to Level 3 (L3) content, including detailed publications, technical reports, and in-depth analyses that support and document the findings presented.

Integration of external exposome data

Source	"Combination of geographical information system (GIS) data on built and natural environments with new data on micro-scale population statistics." Boshuizen, Peuters et al. paper in preparation
Level of evidence	Suggestive evidence
Approach	We examined correlations between 57 exposome indicators across all Equal Life cohorts. We aimed to gain insights for the reduction of complex datasets, as well as to provide context for guiding design and interpreting results.
Findings	Population density underpins many correlations between exposome indicators. This suggests that the health effects of exposures may vary significantly between densely populated urban, and less-populated rural areas. Examples of correlations between population density and other exposome indicators included: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Built environment indicators (urbanity, traffic-related air pollution and noise, transport-related infrastructure, and single-person and single-parent households), some of which can be explained by causal

Figure 8 Example of a Level 3 (L3) post within the Findings section of the Equal-Life Toolbox. The page provides full background documentation supporting a specific finding, including data sources, level of evidence, methodological approach, and detailed results. L3 posts ensure transparency and traceability by linking high-level summaries and syntheses (L1–L2) to the underlying scientific analyses and publications.

Through this layered structure, the Findings section supports a progressive user journey:

- Orientation and action-oriented overview (L1)
- Interpretation and contextual understanding (L2)
- Access to full scientific documentation (L3)

This approach allows users to engage with the Equal-Life results at different depths according to their needs, while preserving traceability between summaries, interpretations, and original sources.

Overall, the Findings section has been conceived as a key component of the Equal-Life Toolbox, enabling structured access to project outcomes and supporting the translation of research evidence into practical insight and informed action.

2.4 The tools

The Equal-Life Toolbox – Tools page <https://www.equal-life-toolbox.eu/eqltools> is a central component of the Equal-Life digital platform that allows users to explore, access, and interact with a curated collection of tools developed within the Equal-Life project to support exposome research and practical applications. The primary aim of the toolbox is to bridge research evidence on environmental and social exposures with decision-making, planning, and capacity-building activities that can improve children’s mental health and cognitive development across Europe.

Figure 9 Screenshot of the main section in the tools page

The Tools page functions as an organised gateway to a diverse set of resources, each designed to support different stages of analysis, interpretation, and learning (See Figure 9). It is organised into key thematic sections that reflect the broad scope of work undertaken by the project consortium. These categories include exploratory definitions and conceptual models, urban analytics tools, noise and traffic exposure models, stakeholder involvement and training tools, and algorithms for data analysis and health impact assessment. Each category contains individual tools or interactive dashboards with concise descriptions, intended use notes, and direct links to more detailed posts or interactive experiences.

2.4.1 Structure and content

The top of the Tools page introduces five main areas:

Explore Definition: This section links to conceptual models, glossaries, and explanatory content that help situate the exposome framework and fundamental concepts behind the suite of tools. It provides educational context for users new to the exposome concept, which refers to the totality of exposures experienced across the life course, including social, physical, and built-environment influences.

Urban Analytics Tools: This category aggregates tools that link geospatial data and environmental indicators with cohort data to reveal patterns and disparities in urban exposures. These tools are especially focused on supporting exploratory research around urban form, accessibility, green space distribution, and other factors that are analytically relevant to children’s environments. Examples include co-accessibility, CTwalk Map, street network analytics, and greenspace accessibility calculators. These tools integrate open-source geographic data and can be directly applied to real-world urban contexts or research questions.

Urban Analytics tools

Set of tools used to link new data with birth cohorts to offer new insights into aspects of the built and natural environment that are not covered by conventional datasets.

The tools can be helpful to identify factors and developed protocols to include smart noise and air quality monitoring from different cities.

Noise and Traffic Models: Tools in this group offer computational models for estimating environmental noise and traffic exposure from open data sources. Such models are critical for quantifying risk pathways that may impact stress, cognitive load, or other health outcomes.

Noise and Traffic models

We create a detailed description of the external exposome by developing comprehensive data and open-source models for the built and natural environments, air pollution, traffic and noise

Stakeholder Involvement and Training Tools: These include resources designed not only for technical analysis but also to promote engagement with communities, practitioners, and policymakers. They highlight participatory methods, training modules, and frameworks to translate scientific knowledge into actionable insights.

Stakeholder involvement and training Tools

We focus on stakeholder involvement and the development of interventions. We develop tools for participatory activities, frameworks, and guidance aimed at raising awareness about the exposome.

Algorithms for Data Analysis and Health Impact Assessment: This category contains tools and code resources that support integrative analysis, such as statistical modelling, machine learning pipelines, and exposure–health outcome evaluation. These tools are particularly relevant for researchers who aim to combine cohort data with environmental metrics using advanced analytical techniques.

Algorithms for Data Analysis and Health Impact Assessment

We analyze how integrated exposures affect children's mental health and development by harmonizing cohort and school study data. Using machine learning and statistical methods, we model these relationships, considering moderation and mediation effects, to provide insights and recommendations.

Overall, the Tools page is designed to be multidisciplinary and user-inclusive, accommodating users with varying levels of technical expertise, from policy makers and educators to environmental scientists and data analysts.

2.4.2 Tools usability

It is important to note that the individual tools presented in the Equal-Life Toolbox are not hosted directly within the Toolbox platform itself, but are maintained in the original repositories of their respective owners, in line with good practices for software sustainability and version control. The Toolbox therefore acts as a curated access point, providing descriptive tool cards that outline the purpose, scope, methodological background, and intended users of each resource. Where relevant and beneficial for end users, dedicated tutorials and explanatory materials have been produced to support correct understanding and use of the tools.

Several of the tools included in the Toolbox are methodologically advanced and require substantial domain-specific expertise (e.g., in GIS, environmental modelling, data analysis, or programming) to be used effectively. For this reason, their primary target audience includes researchers and technical experts with appropriate background knowledge.

Within this context, the Equal-Life project has deliberately developed two interactive learning dashboards to complement these advanced tools and to support broader communication, training, and capacity-building objectives. **The Interactive Web Dashboard for Urban Exposure Learning** and **the Exposure Explorer – Interactive Learning Dashboard** play a central role in this ecosystem by providing interactive, accessible learning interfaces that help users conceptualise and reflect on environmental exposure pathways, inequalities, and potential health impacts across developmental stages. By lowering the barrier to understanding and facilitating guided exploration and reflection, these dashboards directly support the Equal-Life project's ambition of making exposome science useful, interpretable, and actionable for diverse audiences, including policymakers, practitioners, and educators.

2.4.2.1 *Interactive web dashboard for urban exposure learning*

The Urban Exposure dashboard supports training and capacity-building activities on Equal-Life indicators and urban exposure concepts. It is designed to help learners explore how different urban environments shape exposure pathways—particularly during childhood—through didactic content and short interactive exercises.

Measuring Urban Exposures

Explore key concepts behind Equal-Life indicators through interactive study tools. Designed for researchers, students, and urban planners.

Presentation Mode

10 interactive slides pairing problems with best practices. Includes live calculators and decision tools grounded in Equal-Life deliverables.

[Start Presentation →](#)

Flashcard Mode

Test your knowledge with 10 flip-cards. Includes visual prompts and detailed sourcing for every concept. Great for quick revision.

[Open Deck →](#)

The tool enables users to:

- Understand key exposure indicators (e.g., greenness, accessibility, noise);
- Explore simplified geospatial examples embedded in learning materials;
- Reflect on urban inequalities through guided questions and mini-exercises.

The tool is based on geospatial awareness but does not require advanced geographic computation or GIS interaction from the end user.

2.4.2.2 The exposure explorer – interactive learning dashboard

Exposure Explorer is an interactive web dashboard designed to support training and capacity-building activities on Equal-Life indicators and urban exposure concepts, with a focus on understanding how urban environments influence health outcomes across the life course.

The Exposure Explorer dashboard supports training and educational activities related to Equal-Life indicators and urban exposure pathways. It is designed to help learners explore how different urban environments influence health outcomes—particularly during childhood—through didactic content and short interactive exercises.

The tool enables users to:

- Understand key exposure indicators (e.g., greenness, accessibility, noise);
- Explore simplified geospatial examples embedded within learning materials;
- Reflect on urban inequalities through guided questions and mini-exercises.

2.5 Link to the EHEN network resources

The toolbox is connected to the resources of the EHEN network in two ways:

The metadata catalogue, available on the MOLGENIS platform, aims to make information about the variables used in different projects accessible, derived from various data cohorts (Link to the EHEN Catalogue).

By publishing a link on the EHEN toolbox site that connects the Equal-Life Toolbox to the other toolboxes of different projects within the network <https://www.humanexposome.eu/toolbox-search/>.

The assessment of the toolbox, therefore, aims to ensure that these components are well-structured, user-friendly, and effectively communicate the complex findings of the Equal-Life project to a diverse audience, ultimately facilitating the application of this knowledge in real-world interventions and policies. The ongoing development and assessment are iterative processes, driven by continuous feedback from stakeholders to maximise the tool's impact.

3. Methodology and approach

The Equal-Life project adopted a comprehensive and multi-faceted methodology, deeply rooted in principles of stakeholder engagement and co-creation, an iterative development process, and the seamless integration of research findings with practical tools. This approach was essential to ensure the project's outputs were not only scientifically robust but also relevant and usable for a diverse range of stakeholders aiming to improve children's mental health and cognitive development.

3.1 Stakeholder engagement and co-creation

A central tenet of the Equal-Life methodology was the active and continuous engagement with stakeholders throughout the project lifecycle. This was driven by the recognition that to translate research results into effective policies and interventions, the needs and perspectives of those who would ultimately use and be impacted by the project's findings had to be central to the development process. The project implemented a variety of strategies to foster a bi-directional dialogue between the research consortium and (inter)national stakeholders, including policymakers, end-users, regulators, research networks, and even children and parents.

Several key methods were employed for stakeholder involvement and co-creation:

- **Delphi Survey:** This structured communication technique facilitated a dialogue between the Equal-Life project and (inter)national stakeholders. The aim was to translate project

results into effective children's health policies and to incorporate knowledge about best practices and health policies into the project. The Delphi method, relying on a panel of experts, operated on the principle that group judgements are more valid than individual ones, typically involving multiple rounds of questionnaires. The results of the Delphi survey were the starting point of the co-creation process of the toolbox.

- **Co-design Workshops:** These workshops were specifically organised to create interaction with stakeholders (policymakers, end-users) within a design development process. The goal was to ensure that the project's results met their needs and were usable, fostering a sense of co-creation where stakeholders became active participants in shaping the outcomes. Workshops were held in locations such as Skopje and Helsinki, focusing on themes like co-design tools, the application of Equal-Life results, and the translation of scientific findings. These workshops aimed to enable stakeholders to use Equal-Life results for policy making or to draft interventions.
- **Stakeholder Fora:** These platforms were open to a broad range of representatives from institutions, authorities, organised interests, and individual entities across different domains, including higher education, research, associations, and civil society. Fora were organised in cities like Ljubljana, Milan, and Como, providing opportunities for knowledge exchange and interaction between scientists and stakeholders.
- **World Café Discussions:** This format was used within workshops and fora to facilitate discussions around specific questions related to the project's themes, such as the implementation of results into policies, the tools suitable for different stakeholders, and ways to make research findings easily understandable for policymakers.
- **Feedback Integration:** The feedback gathered through these various engagement activities was considered crucial for the iterative design and refinement of the Equal-Life toolbox and guidebook. Stakeholders' insights informed the understanding of their needs, identified examples of good practices and problems to be solved, and provided recommendations for policy use and the features of the tools.

The Equal-Life consortium explicitly acknowledged the importance of stakeholders' involvement in the co-design of efficient and usable tools, particularly the toolbox. The toolbox framework was intended to be defined based on the needs emerging from these discussions, aiming to answer 'Real life' questions from (local) stakeholders using the various modules of the toolbox. Furthermore, stakeholder involvement was recognised as a bi-directional communication process, where learning from and listening to stakeholders was essential from the project's outset. Stakeholders' needs could guide scientific work, including the factors, exposures, and outcomes to be considered, and they could help scientists interpret the results

of data analysis in terms of feasible options for improvement. Even the research questions themselves were developed using a two-fold approach, incorporating both researchers' perspectives and the practical experiences of stakeholders.

3.2 Iterative development process

The development of the Equal-Life toolbox and its associated components, such as the guidebook, followed an iterative and adaptive process. This approach allowed for continuous improvement and refinement based on feedback from both internal project partners and external stakeholders. The iterative nature was particularly evident in the design and implementation of the toolbox, where early prototypes were developed, tested, and then revised based on user input.

Key aspects of the iterative development process included:

- **Prototyping:** Initial prototyping efforts for the toolbox focused on public data, as the project's research results were not immediately accessible in aggregate form. These early prototypes served as tangible objects for stakeholders to interact with and provide feedback on.
- **Exploration and Co-Design:** This phase involved technicians, experts, and potential stakeholders in the activity of designing multiple prototype iterations of the tools. The co-design approach ensured that stakeholder feedback directly shaped the development of the toolbox's structure and features.
- **Usability Testing:** Pilot training sessions, such as those held in Cork and Amsterdam, were crucial for evaluating the usability and accessibility of the toolbox and guidebook. Stakeholders actively used the tools and provided feedback on their ease of use, the clarity of information, and the overall user experience. This feedback highlighted areas for refinement, such as the need for clearer descriptions and simplification of access to definitions.
- **Feedback Loops:** The feedback gathered from workshops, fora, and pilot testing was integral to the iterative cycle. This input was used to identify areas for improvement, refine functionalities, and ensure that the tools met the practical requirements of the end-users. For example, suggestions for further development of the toolbox structure and demonstrator were actively sought and considered.
- **Agile Development:** The project aimed to employ an agile development process with regular iterations and updates to the toolbox based on ongoing stakeholder feedback. This allowed for flexibility and responsiveness to the evolving needs of the users.

The development team adopted a methodology with explorative and creative components, involving successive steps of divergent and convergent reasoning. The innovation approaches relied heavily on four main phases: explorative methodology, implementation methodology, governance methodology (coordinating implementation with long-term strategies and feedback), and dissemination methodology (applying strategies for training and outreach). This structured yet flexible approach enabled the team to adapt the tools based on continuous learning and stakeholder input.

4. Usability report based on website analytics

This section provides an overview of website usage patterns based on analytics data collected over the past twelve months. The analysis is intended to offer a descriptive perspective on how users access and navigate the Equal-Life Toolbox website, highlighting general trends related to traffic volume, access channels, devices, geographical distribution, and navigation paths. The purpose of this section is not to present a formal usability evaluation, but rather to document observed usage characteristics that informed reflections on accessibility, structure, and content organisation. All the images of this section are retrieved from wix internal dashboard connected with the Equal-Life Toolbox.

4.1 Overall traffic and temporal distribution

Over the reference period, the website recorded 1,311 site sessions and 606 unique visitors, indicating a moderate but consistent level of interest in the platform.

The “sessions over time” chart shows a generally stable baseline of activity, punctuated by several pronounced peaks occurring at specific moments during the year (notably around late winter, early spring, and early summer). These spikes are likely associated with dissemination events, workshops, training sessions, or targeted communications related to the Equal-Life project.

Outside these peaks, traffic remains relatively steady at lower levels, suggesting that website usage is primarily driven by project-related activities and outreach moments rather than continuous organic discovery. This pattern is coherent with the role of the Toolbox as a specialised resource intended mainly for project stakeholders and professional audiences.

4.2 New versus returning visitors

Analytics data indicate that the vast majority of visitors during the observed period were new users (approximately 97%), while returning visitors accounted for a small proportion of overall traffic (around 3%). This distribution reflects the current dissemination strategy of the Toolbox, which has so far been promoted mainly through targeted channels linked to project activities, demonstrations, and training sessions.

The limited share of returning visitors does not necessarily indicate low usability, but rather reflects the current stage of the platform and its use primarily as a reference and exploration tool during specific project-related contexts. These observations informed considerations about future actions aimed at encouraging repeated visits, such as periodic updates, newsletters, or additional interactive content.

4.3 Device usage

With respect to access devices, the website is predominantly used on desktop computers, which account for approximately 79% of all sessions, followed by mobile devices (21%), while tablet usage is negligible. This distribution is consistent with the professional and research-oriented nature of the Toolbox, which is typically accessed in work or study environments. At the same time, the non-negligible share of mobile access highlights the importance of maintaining adequate responsiveness and readability across different screen sizes, particularly for stakeholders who may access the platform during workshops, presentations, or training sessions.

4.4 Geographic distribution of users

The geographic distribution of sessions shows a predominantly European user base, with the highest number of sessions originating from countries directly involved in or closely connected to the Equal-Life project. The largest shares of traffic come from the Netherlands, Germany, Spain, Greece, Portugal, and Italy.

This distribution reflects the international composition of the consortium and the locations where dissemination, co-creation, and training activities were organised. It also suggests that the Toolbox has reached its intended core audience within Europe, while still allowing for potential future expansion beyond this initial network.

4.5 Traffic sources

Analysis of traffic sources shows that direct access represents the main entry point to the website, accounting for the majority of sessions. This is followed by referrals from the main Equal-Life project website, which constitute a significant secondary source of traffic. Smaller contributions come from referral links associated with collaboration platforms (e.g. Microsoft Teams), partner websites such as the European Human Exposome Network, and a limited amount of organic traffic from search engines. This pattern indicates that the Toolbox is primarily accessed through intentional navigation, such as direct links shared during project activities or from official project communication channels, rather than through generic web search.

4.6 Navigation and most visited pages

The list of most visited pages shows that the homepage acts as the primary entry point, followed by the main internal sections: Tools, Findings, Guidebook, and Glossary. This navigation pattern confirms the central role of the homepage as a gateway to the platform and suggests that users tend to explore the Toolbox through its high-level structural sections rather than through deep navigation into multiple subpages. At the same time, the analytics indicate a noticeable drop-off after the first or second page visited, with relatively limited depth of navigation. This behaviour is consistent with usage scenarios observed during workshops and demonstrations, where users were often given limited time to explore the platform and focused primarily on specific sections relevant to the session’s objectives.

4.7 Reflections on usability and accessibility

Taken together, these analytics provide a descriptive overview of how the Equal-Life Toolbox has been accessed and navigated during the reporting period. They suggest that the platform has been used primarily as a targeted exploration and dissemination resource, accessed through direct links and project-related channels, and mainly from desktop environments. While no formal usability assessment has been conducted, these observations were used as a contextual input, together with qualitative feedback gathered during stakeholder interactions, to reflect on aspects such as clarity of structure, visibility of key sections, and accessibility across devices. These considerations informed ongoing refinements of the Toolbox layout, navigation, and content presentation, in line with its role as a support tool for understanding and communicating exposome-related research on children’s mental health and cognitive development.

5. Conclusion

The iterative, co-creative design process ensured the tool is aligned with the real-world needs of policymakers, researchers, and practitioners. In fact, The Equal-Life Toolbox successfully integrates scientific outputs into a user-friendly platform aimed at stakeholders engaged in children's mental health and cognitive development. Demonstration events and usability testing (e.g., in Cork and Amsterdam) validated the platform’s functionality and provided insights for refinement. One of the most important achievements includes the alignment between the guidebook and tools, the visual and interactive presentation of findings, and the integration of stakeholder feedback throughout the process. Thanks to this structure, the toolbox enables exploration of complex exposome data and supports the translation of findings into something explorable and understandable for different types of stakeholders.

5.1 Maintenance and sustainability considerations

In line with the long-term vision of the Equal-Life Toolbox as a living and evolving platform, a pragmatic maintenance strategy has been defined to ensure continuity, accessibility, and scientific coherence beyond the formal end of the project. The Toolbox website will remain online and operational for the next two years, guaranteeing continued access to its structure, contents, and integrated resources.

The exact duration of this maintenance period will be further discussed and aligned with RIVM, in accordance with institutional commitments and the long-term hosting strategy described in the sustainability framework.

During this period, the consortium will remain available to support minor maintenance activities, including limited content updates, clarification of descriptions, correction of broken links, and small adjustments needed to preserve consistency with newly released project materials. This maintenance effort is intended to safeguard the quality and usability of the Toolbox rather than to support major functional extensions or redevelopment.

To complement this approach, semi-annual coordination meetings have been scheduled as part of a lightweight governance mechanism. These meetings will serve to review the status of the Toolbox and to discuss potential additions, such as references to newly published scientific articles, follow-up analyses, or dissemination activities directly connected to the Equal-Life project. This ensures that any updates remain scientifically sound, relevant, and aligned with the original objectives of the platform.

Together with the long-term commitments described in the sustainability section—including the use of Zenodo for archiving, integration with EHEN and IHEN resources, and institutional support for hosting—this maintenance strategy contributes to positioning the Equal-Life Toolbox as a stable, credible, and reusable reference point for researchers, policymakers, and practitioners interested in exposome-related evidence and methods.

